

Breast Cancer Detection using Ensemble Techniques in Machine Learning

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Abstract: Breast cancer which is the second most frequent form of cancer in females around the world after skin cancer, is a common disease. The number one killer in the world, breast cancer significantly contributes to this statistic. In actuality, breast cancer is the main reason why women die. The unchecked division and multiplication of cells throughout the body is a hallmark of this illness. In the medical field, numerous studies have been done to differentiate among tumors as benign and malignant early on. Healthcare sector has been profoundly impacted by machine learning technology, which has made it feasible to predict such diseases early and give patients prompt treatment. The Wisconsin dataset, which contains a variety of patient information, was used in this investigation. In this the project's main aim is to predict the disease of breast cancer by using ML algorithms and further comparing the accuracy results of the algorithms. After prediction, ensemble techniques such as bagging and boosting are been implemented in which the algorithms are combined to provide better accuracy or results. The accuracy is been compared with the previous results and is concluded that Ensemble techniques provide better accuracy results in the prediction of the breast cancer.

Index Terms – Breast Cancer, Machine Learning, Ensemble Techniques, Boosting.

I. INTRODUCTION

A report from the Centre for Prevention and Control of Diseases (CDC) claims that cancer in the breast is the prevalent kind of cancer among women. Large variations in breast cancer mortality rates are caused by a variety of factors. The kind of cancer that women possess and the extent of the illness at the moment of their diagnosis are the two crucial variables. This cancer often starts in breast tissue. Breast ducts or lobes are typically where breast cancer initially manifests itself. Your breasts' fatty tissue or fibre connective cells can also get cancerous. Healthy breast tissue usually becomes infected by cancer cells that are out of control, and these cells can then move to the lymph nodes beneath the arms.

Medical professional state that, the cancer develops as a result of breast cells' aberrant proliferation, which has the ability to spread through the lymph nodes to other regions of the body. Early diagnosis and stopping the proliferation of these cells are essential for reducing the disease's symptoms. The first thing a doctor does after diagnosing a tumour is to determine if it is benign or malignant. because the two malignancies have different treatment and preventative approaches. While malignant cells can travel to various parts of the body, cells which are benign are not carcinogenic and cannot do so. With this condition is that there isn't a reliable diagnostic tool available to identify cancer in its earliest stages, allowing the patient to treat as earliest and to attempt to stop the spread of cells which are malignant or tumours.

Any illness that can be treated with some human effort if it is discovered in time. Most people don't notice their illness until it becomes chronic. As a result, death rates are increasing everywhere. when the disease is caught early, before it has had a chance to spread to every part of the body. It is difficult for doctors to establish a therapy plan that might lengthen patient time as the prognosis models are not available. To design the procedure, it requires time that gives the fewest errors. Computerised diagnostic system is needed that employed machine learning techniques. This technology makes use of algorithms to classify tumours, more accurately and quickly identify cells.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The classification algorithms gave result of KNN, Random Forest, Support Vector and Decision Tree (Recursive Division and Conditionally Inference Tree) were compared by Arpita Joshi and Dr. Ashish Mehta [1]. The dataset downloaded by the UCI repository. As a consequence of the simulation, KNN emerged as the top classifier, ahead of SVM, a random forest, and the Decision Tree.

David A. Omondiagbe, and Amandeep S. Sidhu, Shanmugam Veeramani [2] examined the effectiveness of SVM, ANN, the Naive Bayes algorithms using the Wisconsin Diagnose Breast Cancer (WDBC) dataset to ascertain the most efficient method. Based on the simulation's results, SVM-LDA was preferred above the other methods even though it required more computing time.

Kalyani Wadkar, Prashant Pathak, and Nikhil Wagh [3] conducted a comparison study on ANN & SVM to handle the dataset. Multiple classifiers, including CNN, KNN, and Inception V3, were included in the study. The experimental findings and performance analyses revealed that ANN outperformed SVM, making it a superior classifier.

Classification algorithms that are the techniques like the Naive Bayes, the SVM classification algorithm, approaches of Ada Boost, RCNN classifier, and reciprocal recurrent neural networks (HA-BiRNN), Badal Soni, and Sudheer Reddy K Anji Reddy Vaka, [4] provided a new method for identifying breast cancer. The DNN algorithm surpassed other techniques with respect of both performance and efficiency, which are essential variables in contemporary medical systems. They conducted a comparison study among artificial intelligence techniques as well as the suggested approach (Deep Neural Network with Support Value). Other methods, however, didn't work as well.

Using machine learning techniques like the CNN technique, Random Forest algorithm, supported vector machine (SVM), and Bayes methods, Abdullah-Al Nahid and Yinan Kong [6] developed an original approach for predicting cancer by image classification. Although kernels, that have been utilised in image classification, are frequently utilised to extract global features in CNN techniques, the CNN method fared better than other approaches for prediction

Dr. T. Chakravarthy, Anastraj, and Sriram did also a research using same dataset by comparing ML algorithms. Back propagation networks, models of (ANN & (CNN), and support vector algorithms (SVM) were among the strategies examined. For the extraction of features of tumours, the researchers employed ALEXNET's deep and (CNN). The support vector machines was the optimal strategy and delivered superior results, according to the simulation findings (94%).

Vasundhara, Kiranmayee, and Suresh [8] suggested that machine learning techniques could be used to automatically classify mammography images as benign, malignant, or normal. They compared the performance of several methods, such as SVM, and CNN, and Random Forest. The results of their simulations demonstrated that CNN outperformed the other methods, providing accurate classification of digital mammograms by employing filtering and morphological procedures.

The WBCD dataset was used by, Aravind Kumar V, Sivapriya J, Siddarth Sai S, and Sriram S [10] to compare the classification algorithms Naive Bayes, Logistic Regression, and Random Forest SVM,. The results indicated that the highest accuracy (99.76%) given by random forest and lowest error rate among the methods tested. these were performed in an environment which was virtual on the ANACONDA Platform.

III. METHODOLOGY

The methodology adopted for this project is to use classification algorithms of ML such as Logistic Regression, Random Forest, KNN and SVM for the prediction of Breast cancer whether the tumour is benign or malignant. Further, Ensemble techniques or algorithms and boosting which includes Gradient Boosting, Adaptive boosting and XGboost has been used to combine the algorithms and predict better accuracy than given by the individual algorithms. The data set used here in this project is Wisconsin Breast Cancer Data from UCI repository.

IV. ABOUT BREAST CANCER

Breast cancer may appear anonymously in the breast. The primary structural components of the breast are ducts, and connective tissue and lobules. Milk is created by lobules and then flows to the nipple through ducts. Fibrous and fatty cells make up the connective material, which encircles and holds everything together. The majority most breast cancers originate in the ducts or lobules. Lymphatic and blood vessels are two ways that cancer of the breast can spread outside of the breast. A cancer of the breast that has spread is one that spreaded to different or various other body parts. The breast cancer hallmark is unchecked breast cell growth. There are various other types of this cancer depending on the breast cells that transform into the disease.

One of the warning signs or indicators of breast cancer may be breast tissue that is larger or lumpier than the remaining tissue of the breast. alterations in a breast's shape, size, or appearance, as well as irregularities in the skin of the breast, including dimpling or a newly turned nipple. The pigmented skin that is around the breasts etc nipple (areola) peels, levels, crusts, or flakes. Above your breast, there could be a redness and pitting that resembles orange

V. CAUSES & PRECAUTIONS

The reason behind the development of breast cancer is when specific breast cells grow and continue to divide and proliferate more quickly than healthy cells, causing the development of a tumour or lump. Through the breast, these cells can disperse to other areas of the body, such as the lymph nodes. The most prevalent kind of breast cancer is called invasive ductal carcinoma, or ductal carcinoma which arises from cell in the milk-producing ducts. Breast tissues and cells, particularly the glandular tissue referred to as lobes may end up in breast cancer. According to studies, a number of variables, including hormonal, behavioural, and environmental ones, may raise the risk of breast cancer. It is still unknown, nevertheless, why some people with risk factors don't

get cancer while others do who have comparable risk factors do. The complicated interplay between a person's genetic make-up and environmental variables is probably what causes breast cancer.

As you drink more alcohol, your chance of breast cancer increases. The typical recommendation is to limit your intake to no more than one drink per day, according to studies on the effect of booze on the likelihood of getting breast cancer. Maintain a healthy weight. Despite the fact that you are already at a healthy weight, work to maintain it. Ask your physician for advice on the best weight-loss methods if necessary. You should gradually increase your exercise while lowering your calorie intake each day.

According to studies, drinking alcohol raises your chance of getting breast cancer. A single alcoholic beverage per day is often advised because even a tiny amount of alcohol might raise danger. Workout to keep up your healthy weight if you are already at it. If required, ask your doctor for guidance on the most effective weight-loss strategies. You should progressively increase your workout while cutting back on your daily caloric intake. Be active physically. You can avoid breast cancer by being active frequently and eating healthily. Aim overall at least 150 hours of moderate aerobics or 75 minutes all intense aerobics per week for a majority of healthy individuals.

The protective effect increases with breastfeeding duration. Limiting postmenopausal women's usage of hormone treatment may also lower their chance of developing breast cancer. It is advised that you examine the advantages and disadvantages of hormone treatment with your doctor because combination oestrogen therapy may raise your chance of breast cancer. Medication and nonhormonal treatment may be capable to assist you in controlling your symptoms

VI. DATA COLLECTION

The very first process in the prediction of diabetes dataset is the accumulation of data from medical patients which is required in the prediction of diabetes. The datasets include various body parameters as shown below. Large amounts of data are acquired and processed beforehand to train an algorithm as one of the crucial steps in the method of machine learning. For machine learning algorithms to discover patterns and relationships and generate reliable predictions or choices, a large amount of data is necessary.

6.1 Data Defining & Distribution

Machine Learning algorithm works upon datasets. The algorithm builds up a model which is needed to divide the data and do comparative analysis for the accurate results. For the model, different attributes of patient's health is required in prediction of the disease. They describe the features of the picture's discernible nuclei cell. On datasets, the machine learning algorithm operates. In order to get reliable findings, the algorithm creates a model that is used to categorise the information as well as do comparative analysis.

The dataset which is being used in the paper is WBCD i.e., Wisconsin Breast Cancer Dataset imported from Kaggle. The raw information and facts is called data which is unprocessed and needs to be processed so that we can gain information useful for us from the data to be used in the situation wherever needed according to the environment.

```
In [112]: data.head() #printing first five rows
```

```
Out[112]:
```

	id	diagnosis	radius_mean	texture_mean	perimeter_mean	area_mean	smoothness_mean	compactness_mean	concavity_mean	concave points_mean	...
0	842302	M	17.99	10.38	122.80	1001.0	0.11840	0.27760	0.3001	0.14710	...
1	842517	M	20.57	17.77	132.90	1326.0	0.08474	0.07864	0.0869	0.07017	...
2	84300903	M	19.69	21.25	130.00	1203.0	0.10960	0.15990	0.1974	0.12790	...
3	84348301	M	11.42	20.38	77.58	386.1	0.14250	0.28390	0.2414	0.10520	...
4	84358402	M	20.29	14.34	135.10	1297.0	0.10030	0.13280	0.1980	0.10430	...

5 rows × 33 columns

Fig 1. First five rows of the dataset

VII. DATA PREPROCESSING

It is the most crucial step. Pre-processing involves removing undesirable data qualities and other contaminants from the data. Datasets collected from medical patients frequently contain null values, missing values, and other impurities that lead to errors in the data's computation. Unwanted data also degrades the product's quality. Hence, data pre-processing is done to increase the effectiveness and quality of the data. This procedure is required in order to successfully apply machine learning algorithms to the datasets for accurate results and successful prediction. On the provided data, data pre-processing is carried out in two steps:

Missing Values Removal: In this process, the data which has the value of 0 (zero) as worth is eliminated. Other unwanted data is also removed in this process. Doing so, helps to work faster and it also reduces the rate of error in the process of analysing the data. In the fig. given below the data has been analysed and null values are been checked whether is present in the dataset or not. And, we can surmise that there are not a single null value present in the dataset

```

Out[123]: id          0
          diagnosis   0
          radius_mean  0
          texture_mean  0
          perimeter_mean  0
          area_mean    0
          smoothness_mean  0
          compactness_mean  0
          concavity_mean  0
          concave points_mean  0
          symmetry_mean  0
          fractal_dimension_mean  0
          radius_se    0
          texture_se   0
          perimeter_se  0
          area_se      0
          smoothness_se  0
          compactness_se  0
          concavity_se  0
          concave points_se  0
          symmetry_se   0
          fractal_dimension_se  0
          radius_worst  0
          texture_worst  0
          perimeter_worst  0
          area_worst    0
          smoothness_worst  0
          compactness_worst  0
          concavity_worst  0
          concave points_worst  0
          symmetry_worst  0
          fractal_dimension_worst  0
          Unnamed: 32    569
          dtype: int64

```

Fig 2. Data set showing the no. of null values

Splitting Of dataset: The dataset used for training and the test dataset are typically created from the available data throughout the data analysis process. To make sure that all qualities are calculated on the same scale, this is done. Using the logic and methods used for the training dataset, the model is created. The accuracy if the model on unobserved data is then assessed using the test dataset. By carrying out this, we can determine if the model is too good or too bad for the data. A crucial step in creating and assessing machine learning models is splitting the data into test and training datasets.

```

In [24]: # SPLITTING DATA INTO TRAINING DATA & TESTING DATA
          X_train, X_test, Y_train, Y_test = train_test_split(X, Y, test_size = 0.2, random_state = 0)

In [25]: X_train.shape
Out[25]: (455, 32)

In [26]: X_test.shape
Out[26]: (114, 32)

In [27]: X.shape
Out[27]: (569, 32)

```

Fig 3. Splitting of data into training & testing dataset

VIII. ML ALGORITHMS

When the data is been ready for the further process in prediction of Cancer. Machine learning algorithms are applied onto the datasets. Various methods of ML algorithms are included in the model building to analyse data and then for prediction of the results or consequences with great accuracy and precision. They are computer programmes that, without human involvement, can take advantage of information and get better with experience. Teaching approaches could involve discovering the function that converts input to output, discovering the subspace in unlabeled data, or using "instance-based learning," which assigns a label to new instance or (row) by comparing it from either the training data that were previously memorised. An abstraction from particular instances is not produced by "instance-based learning."

8.1 SVM

SVM are a well-known and popular algorithm known as support vectr machines that can be utilized to address a wide range of problems, both linear and nonlinear, as well as practical classification and regression problems. In order to divide data into distinct classes, SVMs seek to establish a line or hyperplane, and this technique has widespread usage in machine learning. SVMs use

hyperplanes, to accurately classify data points into different classes. This approach is beneficial in creating a resilient decision boundary capable of accurately classifying new data points. The position and direction of the hyperplane are significantly influenced by the data points closest to it in a support vector machine (SVM). These support vectors allow us to raise the classifier's margin of error. The hyperplane's location will vary if the support verticals are eliminated. SVM is considered one of the most effective classifiers since it works best with high dimensional data and when there is a clear line of separation.

8.2 KNN

A popular machine learning method that may be utilised for problems with both regression and classification is the K-NN algorithm. Its underlying assumption is that any data points which are similar to one another are probably near together. The method examines the training set for the k nearest neighbours to categorise a fresh point of data, then assigns the majority of the class label to this new point. The k-nearest neighbours are used to forecast outcomes after the algorithm determines the separation between data points. The drawback is the rate of working of the algorithm, The rate of working generally decreases when the data set points get increased. So, It is considered to be as the lazy prediction technique. Here, K defines the number of nearest neighbours, which is always a positive integer. The algorithm then chooses the points that are closest to the arrival point in terms of distance. Several methods are employed to estimate this specific distance, but Euclidian distance is the one that specialists most frequently utilise. The KNN technique can handle enormous data sets and is extremely easy to build, but it has a significant computational cost because it must calculate the distance between each data point in each training sample and must also constantly decide the value of K, which could make the algorithm more complex. The distance among the two close data points is defined by Euclidean Distance.

8.3 Logistic Regression

Predictive analysis frequently use the well-liked supervised learning approach of logistic regression. It is based on the idea of probabilities and is frequently used in a variety of classification tasks, including the identification of diabetes, spam, heart illness, liver disease, and cancer. One of the simplest methods accessible for classification issues, this approach implies a linear connection between input variables and result. When it comes time to categorise or separate data objects into categories, we employ this algorithm. The data is only classified into binary forms of 0 and 1. Logistic regression is therefore employed when there are categorical data. Instead of forecasting anything continuous, logistic regression forecasts whether something is true or untrue. It serves as a classification tool. The dependent variable's independent variable is transformed using the sigmoid function into a probability expression with a range of 0 to 1. It is a well-liked Machine Learning approach because it can offer probabilities and categorise fresh samples using continuous and discrete measurements.

8.4 Random Forest

Another supervised learning-based machine learning method is the Random Forest algorithm. This is also used to address classification and regression issues. It employs the ensemble learning approach, which combines a number of learning algorithms to address any complicated issue. Compared to other algorithms, this learning offers better and more accurate predictions or results. The ensemble approach is used to minimise the noise and variance mistakes that frequently occur in models. A sort of ensemble learning technique known as the Random Forest algorithm is frequently used to handle several datasets. Leo Breiman invented this algorithm. Random Forest models, supervised learning techniques that combine numerous Decision Trees, can improve the accuracy of Decision Trees. By repeatedly partition the source set based on the value of attributes checks, conditional inference trees or recursive partitioning may be utilised to create a decision tree. A statistical method called a conditional inference tree corrects for multiple testing and uses non-parametric tests as splitting criteria in order to prevent overfitting. Tuning the hyper-parameters is necessary because it has a propensity to over-fit. The very first step in this model is to make correct choices and use the algorithm to create a decision tree for better prediction. The prediction result is stored and then voting is done for the result. The result or the prediction which has the highest number of votes is taken as preference.

IX. TESTING & TRAINING ACCURACY OF CLASSIFICATION ALGORITHMS

After using the suggested techniques, the accuracy of different models, including logarithm regression, K-Nearest Neighbours, the Support Vector Machine, and randomly generated forest Classifier, will be measured and calculated. To make it easier to analyse and compare the findings, the precision of the models based on the data used for training and testing will be contrasted and summarised.

Out[151]:

	Model	Training Accuracy %	Testing Accuracy %
0	Logistic Regression	95.164835	94.736842
1	K-nearest neighbors	94.945055	93.859649
2	Support Vector Machine	63.736264	58.771930
3	Random Forest Classifier	100.000000	97.368421

Fig. 4 Accuracy Result

X. ENSEMBLE LEARNING

Ensemble methods involve creating multiple models and combining them to achieve better performance. Ensemble techniques typically produce more accurate predictions than a single model would. They are a kind of machine learning method that combines many base models to produce a single prediction model that outperforms all of the others. Ensemble techniques have been employed in the winner solutions of various machine learning contests, demonstrating their efficacy. The renowned Netflix Competition winner put a powerful collaborative filtering algorithm to work using an ensemble technique. Another example is KDD 2009, when the winning entry also made use of ensemble methods. Voting, stacking, bagging, and boosting are some of the most well-known ensemble methodology procedures. The two simple ensemble methods are voting and averaging. They are simple to comprehend and put into practise.

Voting is utilised for classification issues, whereas averaging is a solution for regression problems. Both approaches begin by creating a number of models from a training dataset. These foundational models can be produced by utilising several splits of a single training set and the exact same algorithm, a single data set and other methods, or any other method. Then, a final forecast is created by combining the results of various models. Voting includes choosing the fundamental model prediction that is made for classification that is most often, as opposed to averaging, which involves calculating the mean of the base prediction models for regression. The utilisation of the same training dataset with several algorithms is demonstrated in the following pseudocode written in Python. To set up an ensemble learning approach that will be clustered later, the base models are required first. There is only one base learning algorithm utilised in the Bagging and Boosting methods. This is because we will be working with uniformly weak learners who will receive varied training.

10.1 Bagging

Bagging, short for Bootstrap Aggregation, is a technique that reduces the variance of a prediction model. It trains multiple learners simultaneously by fitting them independently of each other. Bagging generates more training data by using the original dataset to create new data through bootstrapped resampling, which may include some repeated observations. Each ensemble member has an equal likelihood of being present in every given new dataset. Parallel model training on these datasets produces final ensemble predictions by averaging the results from each model. The majority vote achieved during the voting procedure is taken into consideration when categorising anything. Bagging lowers variance and modifies the forecast to reflect the expected outcome. Machine learning bagging may be developed using these approaches. The original data set is divided into many equal-sized subsets. The replacement observations are chosen. Every subset is given a basic model. All models are acquired concurrently with the training set. These models don't relate to one another. The forecasts from all the models are combined to create the final predictions.

10.2 Boosting

Boosting is an ensemble learning technique that combines multiple weak learners to create a strong learner with reduced training errors. It works by sequentially fitting models to random samples of data and adjusting the weights of data points based on the errors of the previous models. During each iteration, the weak rules generated by each classifier are combined to produce a powerful prediction rule. This iterative process continues until a predefined stopping criterion is met or no further improvement in performance is observed. Boosting techniques attempt to increase prediction accuracy by repeatedly fusing weak learners to create a strong learner. Models with weak learning capabilities categorise data just marginally more accurately than chance. In some cases, boosting can generate more precise forecasts than neural network algorithms or SVM distinct boosting approaches, which may be generally divided into other divisions, have distinct specialised procedures for merging and developing weak learners.

10.2.1 Adaptive Boosting

Adaptive boosting, or AdaBoost, was developed by Yoav Freund and Robert Schapire. The technique aims to reduce the training error by iteratively identifying misclassified data points and adjusting their weights. The process continues until the strongest predictor is obtained. AdaBoost uses a series of weak learners that are trained on weighted versions of the training data. Initially, all data points receive equal weights, and the first learner makes predictions. When a data point is misclassified, its weight is increased, and the next learner focuses on the data with the highest weight. The process continues until no further improvements are observed in accuracy or the number of models.

10.2.2 Gradient Boosting

Jerome H. Friedman developed gradient boosting, which builds an ensemble by sequentially adding predictors that correct the errors of the previous ones. This technique differs from AdaBoost, which adjusts the weights of data points, in that gradient boosting focuses on the residuals of the prior predictor. By combining gradient descent and boosting, gradient boosting optimizes a cost function, and its name reflects this combination of techniques. This is a highly well-liked boosting method that functions quite similarly to AdaBoost. Gradient Boosting corrects earlier mistakes by gradually adding the under fitted predictions from the preceding predictors to the ensemble. What it does compare to the inadequate values of its forerunner makes a difference. This method attempts to adapt the newly developed prediction to the remaining mistakes made by the prior predictor, in contrast to AdaBoost, which modifies the particular case weights at each interaction.

XI. FINAL RESULT & COMPARISON

	Model	Training Accuracy %	Testing Accuracy %
0	Logistic Regression	95.164835	94.736842
1	K-nearest neighbors	94.945055	93.859649
2	Support Vector Machine	63.736264	58.771930
3	Random Forest Classifier	100.000000	97.368421
4	Ada Boost	99.780220	96.491228
5	Gradient Boosting	98.681319	97.368421

Fig 5. Accuracy Result for training & testing dataset**XII. CONCLUSION**

The aim of the project is to discuss and study about the ML algorithms technique which are being used to build a model for early Breast Cancer prediction among the patients based on the datasets which is collected from the patients. The data Wisconsin Breast Cancer Dataset is been gathered from Kaggle website. Detection of cancer in its early stage is one of the major medical problems in the current scenario. Early prediction could lead to a better treatment and life. Algorithms such as SVM, Logistic Regression, KNN and Random Forest have been discussed in the paper. And, then Ensemble techniques are used to combine all the classifiers for giving a better accuracy for prediction. After implementing the Boosting techniques that are Adaboost and Gradient Boosting algorithm, we can conclude that the latter predicts the best accuracy among all the algorithms. Any machine learning challenge aims to choose a single model that can most accurately forecast the desired result. Ensemble approaches consider a wide range of models and average those models to build one final model, as opposed to creating one model. These algorithms are used in building up the model for Cancer prediction. Machine learning will be highly useful in our healthcare sector as a result of technological advancements. The development of these models can also be applied to the detection of other serious disorders. Our generation and the generations to come will benefit from early disease prediction. Yet in order to live a healthy existence for the rest of their lives, people should also adjust their lifestyle and adopt a correct routine.

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